

Biomechanical Analysis of Exo-Assisted Rehabilitation for Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis Patients: A Proof of Concept Study

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Abstract—The treatment landscape for neurodegenerative diseases is advancing thanks to integrating exoskeletons in rehabilitation strategies. This paper presents a proof of concept study on the design of an exoskeleton-based rehabilitation approach for Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) patients. The research aims to define an objective assessment of this pathological condition through the collection of biomechanical data, categorize the disease state, and provide assist-as-needed exoskeleton rehabilitation. The preliminary study was conducted on a healthy subject to test the feasibility and validity of the experimental setup and protocol, using an upper-limb passive exoskeleton and Electromyographic (EMG) sensors during some daily living tasks. The results of this study showed a reduction in the selected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for some muscles using the exoskeleton. In the next steps of the research, the study will be extended to people with ALS, increasing the number of sensors and KPIs to develop the best assistive strategy for an active exoskeleton.

I. INTRODUCTION

Exoskeletons are wearable robots that operate in close cognitive and physical interaction with the human user [1]. In recent decades, they have rapidly found significant applications in rehabilitation, improving the patient's quality of life and reducing the workload of physiotherapists. This work aims to collect and analyze data to develop the best control strategy for exoskeletons, providing personalized assistance that improves

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Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) patients' mobility and quality of life. The main idea is to acquire a large dataset of biological and biomechanical signals from ALS patients to facilitate the categorization of the disease state and the creation of a performance assessment model. Acquisitions include surface electromyographic (EMG) signals and biomechanical data collected by sensors and cameras during physiotherapy activities. The choice of an exoskeleton rehabilitation approach must take into account: field of application, body part to be supported, and actuation technology. Based on actuation technology, exoskeletons are divided into active and passive types. Passive exoskeletons rely on mechanisms such as springs and elastic supports to provide assistance without using motorized components. In contrast, active exoskeletons, equipped with motors or actuators, can adapt to the user's subjective states, but present the primary challenge of delineating the optimal parameters to quantify the user's capabilities and preferences and to develop a subject-dependent control strategy. Given this main challenge, the application of exoskeletons to ALS patients represents a promising but still underexplored field. ALS is a progressive neurodegenerative disease characterized by progressive degeneration and death of motor neurons, leading to the loss of motor abilities. Approximately two-thirds of patients develop a spinal onset phenotype with muscle weakness and wasting in the upper or lower limbs [2], affecting their capability to perform Activities of Daily Living (ADLs). Since there is no cure for ALS and the progression of the disease cannot be predicted, it is crucial to develop new assistance strategies to improve patients' quality of life. This study is designed to acquire data from healthy and ALS subjects, exploring different phenotypes of the disease, with a focus on the 'Flail Arm' (FA), characterized by predominant upper limb weakness without significant involvement of the lower limbs.

II. METHODS

A. Participants and Recruitments

The preliminary study involved a healthy subject without neuromuscular diseases. The experimental protocol of the complete research, accepted by the Ethics Committee, provided for the recruitment of healthy subjects and ALS patients aged between 50 and 70 years and weighing less than 100 kg. Recruitment is conducted through direct contact and promotional announcements, and all participants provided informed consent before the beginning.

B. Experimental Setup

The preliminary phase has included using a passive exoskeleton on a healthy subject to provide shoulder support for all tasks requiring the elbow to be raised above shoulder level. Surface EMG sensors were applied to the participant's muscles (*first dorsal interosseous, abductor digiti minimi, flexor carpi radialis, extensor carpi radialis, biceps brachii caput longus, triceps brachii caput longus, medial deltoid, and descending trapezius*) to acquire EMG signals. Additionally, a camera was used to record the execution of activities, and an IMU was used to provide information on pose, speed, and acceleration during the movements. All listed devices are BTS Bioengineering products. Moreover, Aruco Marker was placed on shoulder, elbow, and wrist to map the relative movements of the arm joints over time. The healthy subject performed exercises to determine the maximum voluntary contraction (MVC) of the muscles of interest. Subsequently, he performed three different tasks with and without the exoskeleton: *Lifting Arm, Pick & Place* and *Drinking*. EMG signals were acquired according to SENIAM guidelines and processed with notch filtering to eliminate power line interference, 20-400 Hz band-pass filtering, rectification, and 4 Hz low-pass filtering. Finally, all EMG signals were normalized to the MVC to ensure consistency and comparability within the subject's data. From EMG signals the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in the time domain were extracted: root mean square (RMS) and integrated EMG (iEMG). Although these metrics have a lower computational complexity than frequency domain metrics, they provide a robust and straightforward quantification of muscle activity, facilitating the analysis of muscle effort reduction using the exoskeleton. During the *Lifting arm*, the subject was asked to raise both the hands above the head. By using the dominant hand, the *Pick & Place* asked to move an object from one point to another, and vice versa. Finally, *Drinking*, requested to simulate the action of drinking from a bottle of 1 Kg. Each task was performed twice in the same recording session. Besides these activities of daily living, a trained neurologist from the ALS center of Federico II University Hospital recorded the scores obtained from dedicated scales, such as *Brooke Scale* and *ALFSRS-r*.

III. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The following results focus on the *Lifting arm* task. A reduction in muscle activity was observed in the Biceps and Deltoid muscles when using the exoskeleton. As shown

in Fig. 1, these muscles present, with respect to the case without exoskeleton, a reduction of the RMS and iEMG values respectively of the 59,6% and 60,5% for the Biceps and 32,4% and 36,1% for the Deltoid, emphasizing the effectiveness of the exoskeleton in reducing muscle effort during the task. These results showed the potential of the approach, which could make a significant contribution to a disease such as ALS, which has a non-linear degenerative course and is still the subject of studies. Thus, this research aims both to provide an objective biomechanical analysis of upper limb functionality in patients and healthy subjects and to subsequently define a tailored robot-assisted rehabilitation approach. In the next stages of the work, we planned to assess a broader set of KPIs for the ALS subjects involved. In particular, additional parameters related to EMG signals will be introduced, such as mean frequency and median frequency. In addition, through inertial information and the mapping of Aruco Markers placed on anatomical joints, metrics related to movement kinematics, such as sparc, range of motion and task execution time, will be assessed [3]. Finally, based on the metrics derived and the construction of the relevant dataset, we aim to develop a new control strategy, taking into account muscle synergies and kinematic movements, to define control hyperparameters that allow the patient to perform rehabilitative exercises following ideal movement patterns.

Fig. 1. (Left) RMS Values for each acquired muscle during 'Lifting Arm' task. (Right) iEMG Values for each acquired muscle during 'Lifting Arm' task.

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